

STUDY THE CORRELATION AND REGRESSING OF SORGHUM SHOOT FLY EGG LAYING IN RELATION TO DIFFERENT DATES OF SOWING OF THE *KHARIF* SORGHUM.

Aher S. D., Ilyas Md. Dake R.B.

Sorghum Research Station,
Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani.sandipaher7878@gmail.com.

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Abstract

The observations regarding the number of egg laid due to shoot fly recorded on five different sowing dates and four different cultivars in kharif season at Sorghum Research Station Parbhani. Correlation resulted that different weather parameter were, rainfall found negatively non significant correlation (except significant in 15 July in CSH-14 cultivar), positive correlated in case of 25th July sowing date. Also maximum temperature and minimum temperature showed positive non-significant correlations except some of dates and cultivars showed negative non-significant correlation. Whereas morning relative humidity was positively non-significant correlation.

Key words- Sorghum Shoot fly eggs- correlation and regression.

Introduction

Sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench] is an important cereal crop in India popularly known as 'Jawar', or 'Great millet'. The benefit of this cereal crop is that it can be cultivated in both *Kharif* and *Rabi* season. Sorghum is an important feed and food crop in the world and utilized as fodder to feed millions of animals providing milk and meat for human being. Sorghum is nutritious its fodder contains in excess of 50 per cent digestible nutrients with 8 per cent protein, 2.5 per cent fat and 45 per cent nitrogen free concentrate. Maharashtra is the foremost sorghum growing states in the country with an area, production, productivity was 2.23 Million ha, 1.61 Million tonnes and 720 kg ha⁻¹, respectively (Anonymous 2019). In Maharashtra about 18 important insect pests have been recorded on sorghum crop. The major being sorghum shoot fly, *Atherigona soccata* Rondani, stem borer, *Chilo partellus* Swinhoe, sorghum shoot bug, *Perigrinus maidis* Ashmead, earhead bug, *Calocoris angustatus* Lethir, army worm, *Mythimna seperata* Walker, midge fly, *Contarinia sorghicola* Coquillette, sorghum aphid, *Melanaphis sacchari* Zehntner, earhead hairy caterpillar, *Euproctis subnotata* Walker and Ear head worm *Helicoverpa armigera* Hubner.

Materials and Methods

Observations were recorded for shoot fly in each plot and replication on following basis. Shoot fly (*Atherigona soccata*), egg count Numbers of eggs on randomly selected 10 plants per plots were counted on 7th, 14th and 21st day after emergence. Dead heart counts caused by shoot fly was recorded from total plants at 14th, 21th and 28th days after emergence in each of the plot, total plants were observed and per cent dead heart was calculated using Abbott's (1925) formula. Correlation and regression coefficient calculated with the help of ICAR- Central Costal Agricultural Research Institute WASP 2.0 - Web Agri Stat Package.

Number of eggs laid by Shoot fly (*A. soccata*) in kharif sorghum sown on 15 June of 2018 and 2019 (Pooled Data).

MW	Period	Year	Avr. No. of Shootfly Eggs				Rainfall (mm)	Temperature(°C)		Humidity(%)	
			PVK-801	CSV-27	CSH-14	SPH-1641		Max.	Min.	Mor.	Ev.
26	25-1 July	2018	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.0	26.3	31.8	22.3	84	57
27	2-8 July		0.8	0.8	1.0	0.8	48.3	31.8	22.4	87	64
28	9-15 July		0.7	1	0.8	1.2	39.9	28.9	21.9	92	80
29	16-22July		0	0	0	0	48.3	31.8	22.4	87	64
26	25-1 July	2019	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.8	46.9	33.2	22.7	85	59
27	2-8 July		1.1	1.1	1.1	1.2	10.6	33.2	23.1	76	58
28	9-15 July		0.6	0.6	0.4	1.1	34.2	33.5	22.6	83	49
29	16-22July		0	0	0	0	10.6	33.2	23.1	76	58

Second sowing date (25 June) multiple regressions equation were carried out for regression coefficient and regression were formulated; r square (r²) values express 86 prediction of future regression values. The selected weather parameters indicated 15.50 per cent, 17.60 per

$$\text{Dead hearts (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of plants with dead hearts in a plot}}{\text{Total no. of plants in the plot}} \times 100.$$

Results and Discussion

Correlations and regression between weather parameters and shoot fly. Correlation of shoot fly (*A. soccata*) egg laying on sorghum at 7th, 14th and 21st DAE, in general correlation of all five dates of sowings (15 June, 25 June 05 July, 15 July and 25 July) with four cultivars (1.PVK-801, 2.CSV-24, 3.CSH-14 and 4.SPH-1641). Correlation resulted that different weather parameter were, rainfall found negatively non significant correlation (except significant in 15 July in CSH-14 cultivar), positive correlated in case of 25th July sowing date. Also maximum temperature and minimum temperature showed positive non-significant correlations except some of dates and cultivars showed negative non-significant correlation. Whereas morning relative humidity was positively non-significant correlation recorded (except 25th June and 15th July dates or in some cultivars) in all four cultivars in all five sowing dates.

Multiple regressions

Multiple regressions equation egg counts of shoot fly with weather parameters in relation to four cultivars viz., 1.PVK-801, 2.CSV-24, 3.CSH-14 and 4.SPH-1641 in *kharif* sorghum sown on 15 June of 2018 and 2019 (first sowing date).

Multiple regressions equation and coefficient were formulated; r square (r²) values express prediction of future regression values. The selected weather parameters indicated 12.30 per cent, 23.90 per cent, 19.60 per cent and 39.50 per cent variation in respect to cultivars on egg population of *A. soccata*. Hence r square (r²) values are low in per cent so prediction cannot be predicted for future regression value.

cent, 0.80 per cent and 33.70 per cent variation in respect to cultivars on egg population of *A. soccata*. Hence r square (r²) values are low in per cent so prediction for future regression value will be indeterminate.

MW	Period	Year	Avr. No. of Shootfly Eggs				Rainfall (mm)	Temperature(°C)		Humidity(%)	
			PVK-801	CSV-27	CSH-14	SPH-1641		Max.	Min.	Mor.	Ev.
27	2-8 July	2018	0.8	1	0.4	0.5	48.3	31.8	22.4	87	64
28	9-15 July		0.9	1.2	0.9	0.9	39.9	28.9	21.9	92	80
29	16-22 July		0.4	0.4	0.4	0.6	103.4	29.6	21.8	88	76
30	23-29 July		0	0	0	0	39.9	28.9	21.9	92	80
27	2-8 July	2019	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.8	10.6	33.2	23.1	76	58
28	9-15 July		0.9	1.1	1.3	1.8	34.2	33.5	22.6	83	49
29	16-22 July		0.4	0.8	0.6	1.6	11.2	34.2	22.9	79	46
30	23-29 July		0	0	0	0	34.2	33.5	22.6	83	49

Third sowing date (05 July) multiple regressions equation of were carried out for regression coefficient and regression were formulated; r square (r^2) values express prediction of future regression values. The selected weather parameters indicated 32.30 per cent, 33.30 per cent,

32.40 per cent and 32.60 per cent variation in respect to cultivars on egg population of *A. soccata*. Hence r square (r^2) values are low in per cent so prediction for future regression value will be unspecified.

MW	Period	Year	Avr. No. of Shootfly Eggs				Rainfall (mm)	Temperature(°C)		Humidity(%)	
			PVK-801	CSV-27	CSH-14	SPH-1641		Max.	Min.	Mor	Ev.
29	16-22 July	2018	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.4	103.4	29.6	21.8	88	76
30	23-29 July		1.7	2.5	1.7	1.1	2.2	29.9	21.9	83	65
31	30-5 Aug		1.3	1.3	0.9	1.2	0	32.8	21.7	79	50
32	6-12 Aug		0	0	0	0	2.2	29.9	21.9	83	65
29	16-22 July	2019	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.5	11.2	34.2	22.9	79	46
30	23-29 July		1	0.8	1	1.1	64.3	30.6	22.6	81	62
31	30-5 Aug		1.4	1.2	1.2	1	85.4	28.1	21.8	92	85
32	6-12 Aug		0	0	0	0	64.3	30.6	22.6	81	62

Fourth sowing date (15 July) multiple regressions equation were carried out for regression coefficient and regression were formulated; r square (r^2) values express prediction of future regression values. The selected weather parameters indicated 28.90 per cent, 14.20 per cent, 32.40 per cent and 32.60 per cent variation in respect to cultivars on egg population of *A. soccata*. Hence r square (r^2) values are low in per cent so prediction for future regression value will be unspecified.

Fifth sowing date (25 July) multiple regressions equation were carried out for regression coefficient and regression were formulated; r square (r^2) values express prediction of future regression values. The selected weather parameters indicated 20.40 per cent, 20.30 per cent, 22.20 per cent and 28.60 per cent variation in respect to cultivars on egg population of *A. soccata*.

MW	Period	Year	Avr. No. of Shootfly Eggs				Rain fall (mm)	Temperature (°C)		Humidity (%)	
			PVK-801	CSV-27	CSH-14	SPH-1641		Max.	Min.	Mor.	Ev.
30	23-29 July	2018	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.1	2.2	29.9	21.9	83	65
31	30-5 Aug		2.6	3.4	2.7	2.8	0	32.8	21.7	79	50
32	6-12 Aug		2.2	1.4	1.2	1.3	7.2	30.5	22	84	68
33	13-19 Aug		0	0	0	0	0	32.8	21.7	79	50
30	23-29 July	2019	1.1	1.2	1	1.4	64.3	30.6	22.6	81	62
31	30-5 Aug		1.3	1.4	1.6	0.9	85.4	28.1	21.8	92	85
32	6-12 Aug		1.2	1.1	1.2	0.7	62.2	30.5	22	89	65
33	13-19 Aug		0	0	0	0	85.4	28.1	21.8	92	85

Hence r square (r^2) values are low in per cent so prediction for future regression value will be unspecified.

MW	Period	Year	Avr. No. of Shootfly Eggs				Rainfall (mm)	Temperature(mm)		Humidity(%)	
			PVK-801	CSV-27	CSH-14	SPH-1641		Max.	Min.	Mor	Ev.
32	6-12 Aug	2018	2.6	3.2	3	3.6	148.4	30.5	21.5	84	68
33	13-19 Aug		3.1	3.8	3.4	3.7	7.2	28.3	20.5	90	75
34	20-26 Aug		2.4	2	1.8	2	110.2	28.7	21.5	91	73
35	27-2 Sept		0	0	0	0	7.2	28.3	20.5	90	75
32	6-12 Aug	2019	1.1	1.8	1.6	1.4	62.2	32.3	21.5	89	65
33	13-19 Aug		2.6	2.5	2.3	2.7	9.7	32.2	22	80	57
34	20-26 Aug		1.4	1.6	1.4	1.2	1.2	32.3	21.5	80	56
35	27-2 Sept		0	0	0	0	9.7	32.2	22	80	57

Summery Conclusion

Incidence of shoot flies egg laying on five sowing date and four cultivars in *Kharif* Sorghum. The egg laying in respect to correlation and multiple regressions with climatic factors varies from date to date and variety to variety. Correlation weather parameter were, rainfall found negatively non-significant correlation (except significant in 15 July in CSH-14 cultivar), positive correlated in case of 25th July sowing date. Also maximum temperature and minimum temperature showed positive non-significant correlations except some of dates and cultivars showed negative non-significant correlation. Whereas morning relative humidity was positively non-significant correlation. Early sowing dates recorded lowest egg lying as compared to late sowing. Similar trends of shoot fly dead hearts were recorded.

References

1. **Aghav, S.T., Tambe, A.B., Baheti, H.S. and Patil, A.J. (2007).** Studies on seasonal incidence of sorghum shoot fly, (*Atherigonasoccata*Rondani). Asian J. Bio Sci., 2 (1/2): 36-38.

2. **Balikai, R.A. (1999).** Effect of different dates of sowing on shoot fly incidence and grain yield. Insect Environment. 5(2):57-58.
3. **Chandurwar, R.D. and Borikar, S.T. (1992).** Stability of shoot fly resistance in sorghum. J. Maharashtra Agric. Univ., 17(1):19.
4. **Dhaliwal, S. and Arora, R. (1998).** Principle of insect pest Management Kalyani Publ., New Delhi.
5. **Kandalkar, H.G. Wanjari, S.S. Dhope, A.M. Narkhede S.S. and Shekar ,V.B. (1996).** Effect of weather factor on population of shoot fly. PKV Res. J. 20(1):94-595.
6. **Karibaswaraj, S.T. and Sable, K.R. (2003).** Evaluation of different insecticides against shootfly *Atherigonasoccata* (Rondani) infesting sorghum. State level seminar on pest management for sustainable agriculture, MKV, Parbhani (M.S.), pp 52-54.
7. **Shekhar, P.R. (1995a).** Seasonal incidence of sorghum shoot fly *A. soccata* (Rond.) Diptera, J. Insect Sci. 8(1):108-109.